

ABSORPTION OF ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION BY YEAST NUCLEIC ACID SOLUTIONS

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Absorption curves of yeast nucleic acid in the ultraviolet indicate that Beer's law is obeyed by the aqueous solutions of the acid at 2600 Å. In presence of bases the maximum absorption peak shifts from 2600 Å to 2650 Å. The process appears to be independent of the nature and valency of the cations as also of their concentrations, but appears to be due to the presence of OH⁻ ions.

It has been observed ("Advances in Protein Chemistry", Academic Press, Inc., N. Y., 1944, p. 222) that prolonged irradiation of the aqueous solution of sodium thymonucleate for a period of about 83 hours brings about some change in the polymerisation of the nucleate, as evidenced by a decrease of the structural viscosity and streaming birefringence (cf. Hollaender, Greenstein and Jenrette, *J. Nat. Cancer Inst.*, 1941, 2, 23). No inorganic phosphorus or ammonia is observed to be liberated which goes to show that no primary decomposition of the nucleate takes place on irradiation. This is further corroborated by the observation that the absorption curve of the nucleate solution at the end of 83 hours' irradiation is entirely congruent with that of the non-irradiated solution kept as the control. Exactly similar behaviour was exhibited by solutions of yeast nucleic acid on ultraviolet irradiation.

Solutions of both these acids have been observed to exhibit a region of maximum absorption at a wave-length of about 2600 Å (Caspersson, *Skand. Arch. Physiol.*, 1936, 73, suppl. 8); this has been attributed to the pyrimidine and purine components present in the two acids (Caspersson, *Naturweiss.*, 1935, 23, 672), because all the purines and pyrimidines present in the two acids (uracil, cytosine, adenine, guanine and thymine) exhibit maximum absorption at about 2600 Å (Heyroth and Loufbourow, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 3441; 1934, 56, 1728). Both thymo- and yeast nucleic acids yield almost identical absorption curves (vide "Advances in Protein Chemistry", p. 223).

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the absorption curves of yeast nucleic acid at different concentrations of its aqueous solutions in the wave-length region from 2200 Å to 3200 Å to examine if Beer's law is applicable at any wave-length within it. Incidentally it was also observed as to how the absorption curve changed with the addition of alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

Yeast nucleic acid (B. D. H. preparation) was purified by the method of Bungenberg de Jong (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1938, 47, 254). The purity of the specimen was ascertained from absence of phosphates and proteins and by estimations of nitrogen, phosphorus and moisture which were as follows :

Nitrogen (Kjeldahl's method), 15.01% (mean of 3 determinations) ; phosphorus (by conversion into phosphate by reflux with conc. KOH solution for 6 hours and preci-

precipitation with NH_4 -molybdate), 8.93% (mean of 3 determinations); moisture (drying at 105° for 12 hours), 11.02% (mean of 2 determinations).

The N/P ratio was found to be 1.68 which compared favourably with the values obtained previously in this laboratory for other samples of the same substance (cf. Mukherjee and Sarkar, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 63).

About 2 g. of the powdery acid was taken in a clean Jena bottle with a litre of equilibrium water (sp. cond. = 2×10^{-6} mho at 35°), previously sterilised by prolonged boiling and the mixture shaken in a mechanical shaker for about 5 hours. The acid became dispersed in water and the suspension was allowed to stand overnight when bigger particles settled down. The solution was then filtered twice through a well cleaned sintered bed filter (No. 4) and the clear liquid, slightly yellowish in colour and quite transparent, was stored under a layer of pure toluene in a refrigerator at about 4° . Only small volumes of this were taken out at a time for each day's experiment. The solution so prepared was used up to the 10th day and was discarded on the 11th day, because Mukherjee and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*) observed that the solutions did not undergo any change in specific conductance, p_n values and cataphoretic velocity up to the 15th day, counting from the day of preparation.

To ascertain whether the concentration of the solution of yeast nucleic acid would change with time, and also whether the different samples of solutions prepared on different occasions would have comparable properties, the absorptions of these solutions at suitable dilutions were studied from time to time. The results will be understood from the following table where the percentage transmissions of three different solutions, each diluted 100 times, have been presented at three only out of 17 different wave-lengths studied for each dilution for economy of space. The values of wave-lengths are given in millimicrons ($1 \text{ m}\mu = 10^{-7} \text{ cm.}$).

TABLE I

Wave-length.	T r a n s m i s s i o n					
	Soln. A (dil.).		Soln. B (dil.).		Soln. C (dil.).	
	1st day.	10th day.	1st day.	10th day.	1st day.	10th day.
320 $\text{m}\mu$	98.5	98.7	98.2	98.8	97.9	98.6
260	14	14.8	14.8	14.8	14	14.6
220	29	28.8	29.8	29.9	29	30.8

It will be seen that the optical absorption remains reasonably constant at all the wave-lengths studied. Hence, it can be safely assumed that the concentrations of solutions do not change with time within the period of investigation and that the reproducibility of the solutions is satisfactory.

Concentration of the solution, so prepared, was ascertained by precipitating the acid out of a known volume of the solution by alcohol at 0° . The precipitate was filtered through a weighed Gooch crucible and the filtrate was again treated with alcohol when a small quantity of the precipitate again appeared. This precipitate was collected on the Gooch, the process of precipitation repeated twice and the still smaller amounts of the precipitate that appeared were taken. The alcohol was then driven out from the precipi-

tate by allowing it to stand for some time at room temperature (30°). Final concentration was calculated after making allowance for the moisture content of 11%. The concentration of the solutions thus determined came out to be 0.5 g./litre.

Reagents used were of 'pro-analysi' or 'Analar' quality. The equilibrium water used was always sterilised by prolonged boiling. Contaminations from outside, specially dust particles, were avoided as far as possible by scrupulous cleanliness. Solutions of the bases used were standardised by titration with a standard succinic acid solution of 'pro-analysi' quality of E. Merck and these alkali solutions were preserved in an automatic self-filling burette. Access of CO₂ from air was prevented by a soda lime guard tube attached to the burette. The baryta and the calcium hydroxide solutions used herein were almost saturated, their concentrations being 0.226 N and 0.0421N respectively. Thus higher concentrations of these two bases could not be used as in the cases of sodium and potassium hydroxides.

A Beckman quartz spectrophotometer * fitted with a hydrogen discharge tube was used for absorption measurements in the ultraviolet region. The absorption vessels were made of quartz and had equal stratum thickness (1.001 cm. and 0.997 cm. respectively).

Fig. 1

*This spectrophotometer was very kindly lent to this laboratory by the Bengal Immunity Research Institute, Calcutta for which our grateful thanks are due to its Director.

Absorption of nucleic acid solutions of different concentrations in absence of bases was measured in comparison with that of water as the standard, while in the presence of bases the standard used was the solution of the bases itself having concentration equal to that in the mixture. Solutions of each of the bases were also compared with water as regards the optical absorption.

DISCUSSION

The absorption curves at different concentrations of yeast nucleic acid solutions have been shown in Fig. 1 by plotting the optical density ($\log I_0/I$ where I_0 is the intensity of the incident radiation, and I that of the transmitted radiation) against λ , the wave-length. The curves show one maximum at $2600\text{\AA}$ and one minimum at $2300\text{\AA}$ within the region of $3200 - 2200\text{\AA}$. The higher the concentration of the solution, the more prominent do the maxima and minima become. Beyond $3200\text{\AA}$ there is very little absorption and all the curves run almost flat. At wave-length lower than $2300\text{\AA}$, the curves again show a tendency to rise.

The next point examined was whether Beer's law was applicable to the system.

Fig. 2

This point has been clarified by plotting the optical density $\log I_0/I$ at $2600\text{\AA}$ against concentration in Fig. 2 wherefrom it will be seen that the plot is linear. Beer's law is therefore applicable in this region. It has also been incidentally observed that $\log I_0/I$ at minima at $2300\text{\AA}$ also conforms to Beer's law. At other regions Beer's law does not appear to hold so accurately.

To test the point further, the values of the extinction coefficients were calculated for the absorption peaks at $2600\text{\AA}$. It is well known that the optical density is related to extinction coefficient by the equation

$$\log_{10} I_0/I = e.c.d,$$

where c stands for the concentration in g./litre, d for the stratum thickness in cm. and e for the extinction coefficient per unit concentration (1 g.). Assuming the molecular weight of the acid to be that of the tetranucleotide unit, which is represented by the formula $C_{28}H_{48}O_{25}N_{13}P_4$, the molecular extinction coefficient E can be calculated from the formula $E = M \times e$, M being the molecular weight. The following table shows the results of such calculation.

TABLE II

Conc. (g./litre)	I at $2600\text{\AA}$ compared to $I_0 = 100.$	$\text{Log } I_0/I.$	$E.$	Conc. (g./litre)	I at $2600\text{\AA}$ compared to $I_0 = 100.$	$\text{Log } I_0/I.$	$E.$
2×10^{-2}	0.05	3.3	214,995	0.5×10^{-1}	14.6	0.8356	217,757
1.56	0.3	2.523	210,735	0.25	38.0	0.4202	219,008
1.39	0.5	2.30	215,604	0.167	51.9	0.2848	222,212
1.25	1.0	2.00	208,480	0.125	62.1	0.2069	215,672
1.0	2.3	1.6383	213,470	0.05	82.7	0.0825	214,995

The values are reasonably constant, thus proving the validity of Beer's law beyond all doubts. Holiday (*Biochem. J.*, 1930, **24**, 619) observed that ultraviolet absorption by purines also obeyed Beer's law. Thus apparently the absorption by yeast nucleic acid and that by the purines might be related together.

The validity of Beer's law will thus serve one useful purpose. It will do away with the necessity of the analytical method for the determination of the concentration of yeast nucleic acid solution by estimation of nitrogen or phosphorus, both of which are tedious and susceptible to greater experimental inaccuracies. Instead, it will serve to supply a physical method for an accurate estimation. This was further examined by estimating the concentration of two samples of yeast nucleic acid solutions both by alcohol precipitation method, and extinction coefficient method and an excellent agreement was obtained as shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Concentration by alcohol pptn. (g./litre)	...	...	...	0.0194	0.0120
Concentration by extinction coefficient (g./litre)	...	...	...	0.02	0.0125

This finding thus serves to solve a standing difficulty so long experienced in determining the concentration of yeast nucleic acid solutions.

The absorption curves in presence of bases have been shown by graphical representation of two typical cases in Figures 3 and 4. It will be observed herein that although the curves are qualitatively similar there are some important points of difference. Both the maxima (at 2600 Å) and the minima (2300 Å) have shifted to longer wave-lengths by 50 Å units and while the minima have been raised a little, the maxima have been depressed.

TABLE IV

Transmission in solution with

Wave-length.	Soln. with- out base.	NaOH		KOH		Ba(OH) ₂		Ca(OH) ₂	
		1N.	0.00 1N.	1N.	0.00 1N.	0.2N.	0.00 1N.	0.04N.	0.00 1N.
320m μ	99.9	99.3	99.5	98.6	99.2	99.8	99.6	99.0	98.9
310	98.6	99.1	97.8	98.8	98.7	98.8	98.0	98.1	98.0
300	96.1	95.5	95.4	94.3	96.1	96.0	96.0	95.0	95.4
290	84.0	86.0	86.2	84.2	85.8	86.0	85.5	84.3	85.0
280	61.7	62.5	62.6	60.7	61.7	62.0	60.9	60.5	62.0
270	44.0	45.0	46.0	43.1	45.6	44.5	43.0	43.9	44.9
265	39.8	42.8	43.1	41.2	42.1	41.8	41.1	41.8	42.2
260	38.0	43.2	44.3	44.2	43.0	42.0	42.5	42.9	42.8
255	39.0	46.1	47.1	45.3	46.4	44.9	46.0	45.8	45.1
250	42.5	50.3	50.6	48.4	50.0	48.8	50.2	50.2	49.1
245	48.1	54.5	55.1	53.0	54.7	53.1	54.2	54.8	53.6
240	55.8	57.6	58.0	57.0	57.8	56.5	57.1	57.8	56.8
235	62.5	58.1	58.5	57.6	58.4	57.2	58.0	58.0	57.7
230	67.0	53.8	54.7	53.1	54.0	53.5	53.2	52.2	54.2
225	65.8	44.0	44.4	42.3	44.2	44.9	42.8	42.7	44.1
220	55.6	33.8	34.7	33.5	33.5	34.2	32.2	32.2	34.5

All the bases used herein behave exactly similarly irrespective of their nature and concentration as will be evident from Table IV, down to a concentration of 0.001 *N* of the bases and to a 1.25×10^{-4} solution of the acid (p_H of the mixture being 6.7). In the table the transmission (*i. e.*, the values of *I*) have been presented from the extreme concentrations of the different bases used.

A graphical representation of the above will show that the height of the peaks or the depth of the minima appears to be independent of everything else excepting the concentration of the yeast nucleic acid solution on itself.

Fig. 3

Absorption of sodium yeast nucleate solutions has also been studied; the curves exhibit well defined maximum and minimum values of absorption at 2600Å and 2300Å respectively. Beer's law is also found to be valid in this system. In Fig. 3 (and inset) the absorption curves for two solutions of Na-yeast nucleate at two different concentrations out of the several solutions studied have been shown. The molar extinction coefficient has been calculated assuming the molecule of sodium yeast nucleate to be represented by $C_{38}H_{45}O_{29}N_{15}P_4Na_4$ (formed by replacement of four H

atoms of yeast nucleic acid by four sodium atoms). The values of molar extinction coefficients for solutions of different concentrations are fairly constant. The molar extinction coefficient of yeast nucleic acid was found to be 215,000 (*vide supra*), while that for the sodium salt, as calculated above, lies near about 35,000. Therefore, concentrations remaining the same, the sodium nucleate solutions should be more transparent than nucleic acid solutions, as could be seen even visually.

Heyroth and Loufbourow calculated the molar extinction coefficient of thymus nucleic acid solution from a summation of the values of molar extinction coefficients of the individual purine and pyrimidine compounds (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1734). Their value comes out to be 37,000 nearly. While our value for the yeast nucleic acid differs completely from that of Heyroth and Loufbourow for thymonucleic acid the latter agrees with our value for the sodium salt.

This frequency shift in the absorption peak in the presence of bases may be due to one or other following probable causes:

1. Hydrolytic decomposition of the acid in presence of bases.
2. Formation of the corresponding salts.
3. Any other cause affecting the constitution.

It is unlikely that the first of these factors is in any way responsible for this phenomenon in as much as hydrolysis of the nucleic acid is brought about by moderately concentrated solutions of bases at higher temperatures or on prolonged interaction at ordinary temperatures. Dilute solutions of bases appear to have little effect. Even if slight hydrolysis of the acid be effected at low concentrations of the bases, as used herein, nucleotides, nucleosides or at best purines may be liberated, and since the absorption of yeast nucleic acid is ultimately attributed to the purines (cf. Heyroth and Loufbourow, *loc. cit.*) and not to the phosphoric acid or sugars which might be formed but which have no absorption maxima at 2600 Å, it is unlikely that mere hydrolysis of the acid can bring about any frequency shift unless some other processes proceed simultaneously along with it.

The responsibility of the process of salt formation is also ruled out by a close study of absorption by sodium yeast nucleate solutions. The absorption peak in this case too coincides exactly with 2600 Å as shown in Fig. 3 (and inset) where absorption curves of the acid in presence and absence of alkali as well as of the sodium nucleate solutions have been presented. This suggests that mere neutralisation of the acid is not likely to be responsible for the frequency shift.

The only alternative left, to which the responsibility for this phenomenon may be attributed, is the third factor, viz., some intrinsic change in the constitution of the acid. Again, since the phenomenon does not appear to depend on the nature and valency of the cations but occurs with all the bases alike, it is suggestive of that the OH' ions, which constitute the only common factor, might be responsible in this case. This is in a way borne out by the fact that salts of the same cations, like NaCl, KCl, BaCl₂, and CaCl₂, cannot bring about this frequency shift.

The exact role of OH' ions is not quite clear. Holiday (*loc. cit.*) found that in the case of several purines (adenine, caeffine, etc.) increase of p_H to the alkaline side caused the region of maximum ultraviolet absorption of the purines to be shifted through

30Å towards longer wave-lengths. The experience of Loufbourow *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 148) has been similar in the case of uracil. These workers have attempted to explain the phenomenon by lactim-lactam tautomerism of the purines. In the present investigation too, it has been found that with the addition of alkali, if the p_H goes above 7, then only the characteristic frequency shift is observed. Presence of OH⁻ ions thus causes some change in the purines to which can be attributed the responsibility of the frequency shift. Further work is necessary to clarify the point and this is in progress.

The energy change involved per mole in the process of frequency shift from 2600Å to 2650Å can be calculated from the formula

$$\Delta E = N.h. \Delta \nu$$

all the quantities involved having their usual significance. The value comes out to be 2.067 kilo cal. per mole. The energy change involved is thus quite small compared to those in a true chemical process, where breakdown of some orthodox valence bond occurs.

Another point should deserve mention. It is known that nucleic acid molecules are deaggregated on dilution (Mukherjee and Sarkar, *loc. cit.*). Since Beer's law is valid in the region of maximum absorption, it appears that depolymerisation itself has no effect on ultraviolet absorption. This in a way is suggestive of the view accepted by a class of workers (vide Payli and Valko, "Electrochemie der Kolloide", 1929) that the aggregation in such cases occurs by Van der Waal's forces.

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